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Authors:

Ibra SECK (Enda)

Libasse BA (Enda)

Cheikh Abdou Khadre Dieylani DIOP (Enda)

Scientific Reviewer(s): Francesco Gardumi, Maryna Henrysson (KTH)

Editorial Reviewer(s): Suat Sevensan (KTH)

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1. Introduction

In this communication and dissemination plan, we describe the communication strategy (internal and external) and the operating strategy from the first month of project implementation (month 1) until the next update of the plan DCE (month 18).

During this stage of the project, the emphasis will be placed on the development of a first version of the communication strategy and the design of communication tools (logo, graphic charter, website, social networks), the development of a data management plan and the mapping of target networks to be achieved within the framework of the project.

This deliverable proposes an initial dissemination strategy to ensure that project ideas have a broad impact across our networks and targets (policy makers, research centres, universities, national and regional institutions, etc.). The dissemination strategy will be further developed considering the nature of the results, interactions with stakeholders and levels of success of the awareness channels.

2. Targets audiences for communication and dissemination

To achieve the intended objectives of the project, it is crucial to identify all potential stakeholders who need to be informed about the project and its outcomes during the development of the communication and dissemination strategy. To ensure effective communication of the varied project objectives, the plan must consider the specific needs and interests of diverse target groups. Given the project's multifaceted objectives and diverse target groups, Task 6.4 focuses on systematically identifying and mapping target networks. This approach aims to refine communication channels in alignment with the specified objectives and target groups. The strategy will incorporate the characteristics and interests of these identified networks, enabling the delivery of information in suitable formats and tailoring the messages for effective communication.

3. Strategic Communication Plan for the "RE-INTEGRATE" Project

A) External Communication:

i. Overall Objective:

Enhance the visibility of the RE-INTEGRATE project within target communities, with a focus on raising awareness of the challenges the project will meet.

ii. Enhancing Ownership of EU Tools in the Global South:

Actions:

- Launch awareness campaigns highlighting the benefits of AU and EU tools tailored to the needs of target countries.
- Conduct interactive webinars to explain and demonstrate the effective use of tools.
- Develop visual materials and explanatory documents in local languages.

iii. Popularizing New Tools among Targeted Communities:

Actions:

- Develop tutorial videos to make the adoption of new tools more accessible.
- Organise hands-on workshops in communities to encourage on-the-ground tool utilisation.
- Use testimonials and case studies to illustrate the tangible benefits of new tools.

iv. Promotion of Universal Access to Sustainable Electricity:

Actions:

- Conduct awareness campaigns on persistent challenges and innovative solutions for universal access.
- Organise discussion forums involving key stakeholders to develop concrete strategies.
- Establish partnerships with international organizations sharing similar sustainability and energy planning goals.

v. Highlighting Best Practices in Energy Planning within Development Policies:

Actions:

- Conduct virtual conferences showcasing the successes and positive impacts of project tools.
- Create communication materials for policymakers to encourage the integration of best practices.
- Actively participate in international events related to sustainable development and energy planning.

B) Internal Communication:

i) Overall Objective:

Facilitate bottom-up dissemination of energy planning skills, share discoveries, and promote interdisciplinary collaboration.

ii) Internal Awareness and Adoption of Tools:

Actions:

- Establish an online platform to share tutorials, tips, and best practices.
- Encourage active team participation in the continuous improvement process.

iii) Enhanced Internal Social Media Engagement:

Actions:

- Develop a social media strategy to encourage an exchange of ideas.
- Set up and use systematically the online discussion forums to facilitate communication among teams.
- Formally recognise outstanding team contributions via internal social media.

iv) Optimisation of Online Presence:

Actions:

- Use internal communication tools to share real-time project updates.
- Encourage teams to share their experiences and successes on internal social media.
- Organise online Q&A sessions with the project leadership team to promote transparency.

v) Establishment of Dynamic Internal Communication:

Actions:

- Conduct regular internal meetings to discuss progress, challenges, and opportunities.
- Create and disseminate a periodical internal newsletter to highlight team achievements.
- Create and disseminate regularly an external newsletter on the website to reach and get feedback from external target groups and networks.
- Use online collaboration platforms to facilitate ideas sharing and suggestions exchange.

vi) Evaluation and Adjustments:

Actions:

- Ensure the achievement of performance indicators defined within the framework of the project.
- Regularly collect feedback from internal and external users to assess the effectiveness of initiatives.
- Continuously adjust employed DCE strategies based on results obtained and feedback received.

4. Communication Objectives

Creating an efficient communication system is crucial for promoting the grassroots dissemination of energy planning skills, fostering the exchange of findings and assessments, and encouraging cross-disciplinary utilization of results across different fields. The following outlines the measures to ensure the achievement of these goals.

- Strengthen the visibility of RE-INTEGRATE with beneficiary communities:
 - i) Better refine the energy-economy-environment modelling approaches adapted to the needs of the countries.
 - ii) Popularise the new tools to facilitate their adoption and implementation within the targeted communities to overcome the limitations of EU-based tools in addressing the needs of the Global South.
- Promote ownership of energy modelling and planning issues:
 - i) Universal access to sustainable and low-cost electricity remains a challenge for many AU countries.
 - ii) The absence of prospective studies and sustainable modelling tools limits policies in favour of access to electricity and the energy transition in these countries with high renewable energy potential.
- Promote good practices that promote energy planning inside development policies:
 - i) The appropriation and application of scientific results from the tools ultimately contribute to improving climate planning documents (National Determine Contribution – NDC, Biennial Update Report - BUR, etc.) and the economic development of countries.

5. Exploitation strategy

The operational plan, integrated into the WFD strategy, is designed to attain the project's objectives within five years of completion. This timeframe acknowledges the pragmatic and intricate challenges that may impede smooth operations. Striking a balance between ambition and risk management is therefore imperative. Operational activities will empower stakeholder networks to apply the knowledge and modelling tools in their respective contexts for in-depth analysis and outcomes. To enhance accessibility and reproducibility, we will make the models, code, and tools readily available. Identifying key potential users, including decision-makers in business and public authorities at international, national, and sub-national levels, will guide targeted actions. These actions aim to showcase the

project's results' applicability to their specific contexts, ensuring wider dissemination and practical implementation.

In addition, the research infrastructure and applications and the training materials produced by the project are used in training activities at EMP-A (application of several countries including the AU to EMP-A 2024) and the SDS Summer School targeting new analysts and researchers from the 8 AU countries and beyond.

RE-INTEGRATE efforts will focus on delivering precise insights into pertinent analytical methods, concepts, and policy ideas to targeted stakeholders participating in UNFCCC COP events, researchers engaged in ECEMP workshops, LEAP-RE projects (with a particular emphasis on OASIS), and other EU initiatives (such as EPIC Africa and EU Mopo). Additionally, we will reach out to stakeholders within the existing networks established by the project. These interactions are crucial, providing essential input and long-term support for the activities and project networks that form the foundation of the HLPD CCSE partnership's work.

6. Communication Tools and Activities

6.1. Logo and Graphic Identity

The initial objective of designing a comprehensive graphic charter and distinctive logo for the project has been fully achieved. These visual elements embody the idea of collaboration, knowledge exchange and innovation between the two continents in the field of climate-friendly energy strategies.

The design process was meticulous and followed a multi-stage plan. It began with the presentation of an initial version of the logo, which raised questions about the neo-colonial nature of the word RE-INTEGRATE. After several weeks of discussions and revisions, a consensus was reached, avoiding any ambiguity and addressing the concerns raised.

The design stages included the proposal of a colour palette evoking modelling, collaboration, innovation and sustainability. Modern, legible typography was selected to ensure effective use across a range of media.

Regular validation points were scheduled with the ENDA ENERGIE management team within the WP6 to ensure that the graphic design and logo met expectations. Close coordination with the project partners, particularly the communications team, was decisive in ensuring that the graphic design and logo corresponded to the needs and values of the RE-INTEGRATE project.

The realistic timetable set was adhered to, and all the design, revision and finalization stages were completed within the 30-day deadline. Deliverables included a complete graphic charter, a PowerPoint

template, a TORs template, templates for different media (letterheads, leaflets, policy briefs, banners, visuals), and a distinctive and versatile logo, as well as editable source files.

The successful production of the graphic charter and logo is an important step in the communication and promotion of the RE-INTEGRATE initiative. These visual elements play a key role in conveying the project's mission, values and ambition, helping to bring continents closer together through climate-smart energy strategies.

6.2. Zoom and MS Teams

To facilitate coordination and internal communication, the consortium uses tools such as Zoom and Teams. Zoom is used for internal meetings of the consortium (coordination, by WP, for webinar needs, etc.). In addition, the use of MS Teams facilitates the sharing of documents (project, plan, deliverables, etc.) internally and more efficient exchange between members of the consortium and between WP and task managers.

6.3. Website

The development of the website for the RE-INTEGRATE: "Bringing continents together through climate-smart energy strategies" project has reached a significant stage, marking a major step forward in implementing of this ambitious initiative led by KTH and a consortium of universities and civil society organisations.

The website has reached a level of functionality that makes it operational, covering most of the essential information relating to the RE-INTEGRATE project. At this stage, overall progress is estimated at around 70%.

Although it is 70% functional, ongoing efforts will be made to achieve full implementation. Next steps will include the completion of the remaining elements, exhaustive testing, and adjustments based on user feedback. Close coordination with the consortium and the project's communications team will be maintained to ensure that the website fully meets the needs and values of the RE-INTEGRATE project. The successful implementation of this platform will play a key role in the communication and promotion of this important initiative.

6.4. Social Media

The establishment of social media platforms for the RE-INTEGRATE aims to bring continents closer together through communicating the advancements in the development of climate-smart energy strategies and represents a crucial step in our communication strategy. The selected platforms include

X, Facebook, LinkedIn, and YouTube, all playing an essential role in promoting our publications, disseminating key information, and stimulating discussions on energy planning issues.

Currently, the project actively maintains accounts on X, a dedicated Facebook page, a LinkedIn page, and a YouTube channel. These channels are consistently updated with relevant project information, although efforts to enhance engagement and animation are still in progress.

The content created so far includes informative articles on the implementation of the project and a presentation video aimed at raising awareness among our targeted audience. Although the animation could be considered a little timid, we have managed to generate initial interest and spark discussion. The successful implementation of social media is a key asset for the communication of the RE-INTEGRATE project. The progress made so far is encouraging, but we remain determined to strengthen our presence and maximize the impact of our messages on these platforms.

Table 1: Communication Activities Table

Communication activity and means	Target group	KPI (<i>monitoring means</i>)
RE-INTEGRATE's visual identity	All stakeholders	Summary of all the below
Graphical charter	Project partners	Use of project logo and template for all external communications by all partners within M04 (<i>project repository</i>)
Website (domain www.reintegrate.eu will be secured, if still available, or similar)	All stakeholders and civil society	> 1500 unique visitors/year; 30% return visitors; <50% bounce rate (<i>website statistics</i>)
Bi-monthly newsletters	All stakeholders	2500 recipients by M12; > 20% opening rate (<i>newsletter management system's statistics</i>)
Infographics and videos	Decision makers, academia and practitioners	> 500 views of videos and > 500 downloads of infographics by end of the project (<i>video and website statistics</i>)
Press releases and popular science articles	Civil society and other non-state actors and Academia	At least 3 published releases or articles in the project's lifetime (<i>project's newsletter and repository, journal websites</i>)

Social media communications (via Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, WhatsApp boot)	Practitioners, Academia, Civil society	<i>#re-integrate</i> hashtag used 500 times in social media in the project's lifetime for positive comments (<i>social media posts information</i>); 6 project stories published on Twitter/LinkedIn
Networking activities with other EU and LEAP-RE projects, networks, initiatives, partnerships	Academia, Practitioners	> 30 references to the project in websites, reports, etc. (<i>websites information</i>)

7. Dissemination objectives

Table 2: Dissemination table

Dissemination objective	Target group	Measures and KPIs	Task
Ensure stakeholders' engagement in driving the research and analytical work.	Priority Users Group; SAB; other AU Stakeholders	Stakeholder workshops to set up analytical activities (>2 key institutions – utility, funding bodies, government - represented at the workshops for each of the 8 AU countries)	T5.1, T5.2
Provide the stakeholders with practical and usable policy and investment recommendations.	Priority Users Group; SAB; other AU Stakeholders; COP / EMP-A / SDSummer School high-level dialogues participants	Stakeholder workshops, Review of briefs by stakeholders, Organisation of COP side-events, high-level presentations (>25 stakeholder representatives downloading and reviewing briefs by project's end; >100 overall downloads of briefs from Zenodo by project's end; >8 high-level presentations by AU analysts)	T2.3, 3.5, 4.4, 5.1, 5.3, 6.4
Provide supporting information and research infrastructure to existing partnerships in the AU energy and climate landscape and the HLPD CCSE Partnership.	AU-EU Energy Partnership, Africa Green Hydrogen Alliance, CCG Partnerships, other EU projects, energy and climate networks in the AU, LEAP-RE projects	Stakeholder workshops, Bi-lateral interactions (>1 bi-lateral interaction around RE-INTEGRATE outputs with each of the networks by the project's end)	T5.4, T5.5
Share and foster ownership of research infrastructure for 3E modelling by the AU and EU research community.	EMP-A and SDSummer School trainees	(Co-)Organisation of tracks and teaching at EMP-A and SDSummer School (>30 trainees obtaining a certificate of completion from at least 8 AU countries)	T3.3, T2.5

Engage the international teachers and trainers community in the co-creation of teaching and learning material.	EMP-A and SDSummer School trainers; lecturers of AU and EU universities; other EU projects and CCG	Use of workflows for creation and update of courses at EMP-A and SDSummer School (>20 course modules or hands-on exercises co-created or co-updated by at least 2 institutions, of which one from the AU)	T2.3, T2.5
Create enabling environment for multi-lateral knowledge sharing on AU-EU energy modelling challenges and solutions.	Participants of ECEMP, IEW, OpenMod and other conferences; The Turing Way initiative; partners of other EU projects and CCG	Preparation and delivery of (high-level) presentations and workshop sessions by AU analysts at ECEMP, IEW, OpenMod and others (>8 presentations by the end of the project, in presence or online)	T6.3
Create a dialogue and a space for improvement on gender and minorities-related aspects in energy systems modelling and teaching.	AU and EU analysts of different gender identities; AU and EU analysts representative of minorities	Surveys and bi-lateral interactions at the sides of stakeholder workshops and international training (>20 relevant items of feedback obtained from at least 10 recipients by the end of the project)	T2.4, T5.2
Dissemination of RE-INTEGRATE's scientific outputs to the wider research community.	AU and EU researchers, analysts, practitioners	Open access scientific publications (>20 published or submitted with at least one round of review by the end of the project) and 1 Special Issue in ESR or ESD	WP2, 3, 4, 5

8. Data Management Plan

Cf. on Data Management Plan v1 (D6.4).

9. Theory of Change

The project has developed a Theory of Change (ToC) that will guide its implementation. The ToC, represented in Figure 1, outlines the causal pathways linking activities to desired outcomes. This framework articulates the project's underlying assumptions, interventions, and expected impact. Grounded in academic rigor, the ToC serves as a practical roadmap for implementation, enabling effective and reiterative monitoring, evaluation, and refinement. This underscores the project's commitment to transparency, accountability, and evidence-based practice for achieving sustainable outcomes.

Figure 1. RE-INTEGRATE Theory of Change

10. Barriers to achieving the expected impacts and strategy

Concerning the results defined in the project in terms of communication, we have identified an exhaustive list of limits. As such, strategies are defined to overcome these different barriers. We can note:

- Diversity of audiences (networks): this will involve adapting content and communication channels to meet the diverse needs and levels of understanding of stakeholders. Understanding the messages resulting from the results of the models may not be very easy, therefore, with the target networks, it will be necessary to adapt the message according to their level of understanding. Upstream work on the channels to favour and the information to share with each type of target.
- The linguistic and cultural barrier: stakeholders speak different languages and come from diverse cultures. This makes communication a little difficult to harmonize. For this, the information to be shared as well as the website will be put in different languages (English, French, etc.) to reach the linguistic groups.

- Unequal access to technology: Not all stakeholders have equal access to advanced communications technologies, which limits their participation. Facilitate access to results to our target networks through different channels initially. Monitor channel usage (website, social link) to better understand the most appropriate channel for each target. This makes it easier to access all targets.
- Competing for attention: In an information-saturated world, attracting and retaining the attention of stakeholders among other sources of communication can be difficult. We will actively employ strategies to capture the target network's attention by identifying communications spaces where the audiences are engaging with the content already.

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